

GROWTH OF MODERN TERRORISM: CAUSES, TACTICS AND COST OF INTERNATIONAL TERRORISM

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Abstract

Different definitions of terrorism have dominated the discourse both at the national and international level. The term terrorism is difficult to define within political circles. It brings out strong emotions which result in confusion. The paper reveals that terrorism manifests itself through distinctive deployment of a variety of criminal acts calculated to harm human life, property and other interest. The paper notes that terrorism consists of planned acts of violence. the study adopted historical approach. Data was collected from secondary sources namely, textbook, journals, magazines, newspapers and internet materials. Findings reveal that terrorist have a desire to promote change by the threat or use of violence. Some of the tactics employed by international terrorists have inflicted serious damage to and casualties on innocent population, ranges from kidnapping, hijacking, bombing, sabotage and assassination. The paper concludes that weapons symbolize power to the terrorist and their aim is to draw the attention to a cause, to provoke over-reaction by the government in an attempt to undermine public confidence and to promote public fear and an atmosphere of alarm.

Keywords: Terrorism, Tactics International Terrorism, Causes, Warfare.

INTRODUCTION

The meaning of the word terrorism is rarely agreed upon, although scholars have produced a variety of definition. Ostensibly, there are almost as many definitions of terrorism as there are opinion on it. There is no true or correct definition, because terrorism appears as an abstract concept with no real essence. Most scholars agree that terrorism involves the use of violence as a strategy to achieve certain goals, of which is characterized by inducing fear in its innocent victims(Jenkins, 1977). A broadly accepted definition of terrorism is very difficult of work out, because the term is extremely pejorative, because what is terrorism for somebody may be deemed as heroism by somebody else.Quinton (1985), observed that the issue of definition of terrorism is one of the most controversial issues in the contemporary international legal and practical arena. He went further to observe that the international community has not yet established a

comprehensive universally accepted definition of terrorism. Acts of terrorism have continued to engender violent emotions.

The lack of a universal definition of terrorism represents a serious limitations on states ability prevent acts of terrorism. There are also fundamental disagreements among states as to a universal definition of terrorism. Cooper (1978; 105); a renowned terrorism expert also agrees that, terrorism is very difficult to define because it has a pejorative connotation. A person is politically and socially degraded when labeled a terrorist and the same thing when an organization is called a terrorist organization. Crenshaw (1983: 20) argues that, terrorism cannot be defined unless the act, the target and the possibility of success is analyzed. Under this, freedom fighters use legitimate military methods to attack legitimate political targets. Terrorist on the other hand fail to meet the legitimacy test in one of the three categories namely; military methods, military targets and some chance of victory. Furthermore, Crenshaw also suggests that, revolutionary violence should not be confused with terrorism. To Crenshaw, terrorism means socially and political unacceptable violence aimed at innocent targets to achieve a psychological effect.

Mac- Wilson (1992; 76) defined terrorism as, organization violence by small groups against the state or against other ethnic groups or classes or purposely included as potential targets. Mac- Wilson identified four characteristics of terrorists namely;

- i. Terrorism activities are usually undertaken by small and usually secret groups of men and women;
- ii. Terrorist activities are usually organized and involve detailed planning and direction,;
- iii. Terrorism is used to further political aims;
- iv. The target of terrorism is usually the state.

It is important to observe that, not all violent political acts are intrinsically terrorist acts, as witnessed from the many national liberation struggles in South Africa, Angola, Zimbabwe, Namibia and guinea Bissau in Africa.

Terrorism has in recent times become a phenomenon of great concern in world politics. The question of terrorism has not yet been solved with remarkable success. This is due to the fact that different states in the international system have not been able to implement the many articles, protocols and the conventions against terrorism. Terrorism exists for reasons of inequality, exploitation and discrimination; it breeds the kind of resentment that makes some people see violence the only option.

Growth of Modern Terrorism

Terrorism is one of the key concepts in the analysis of contemporary international politics. The term has been abused for propaganda purposes, Terrorism is a weapon or method which has been used throughout history by both state and sub-state organizations for a whole variety of political causes or purposes. There is still considerable disagreement among specialists as to the reasons for the enormous growth of acts of terrorism in the late 1980s and 1990s. Nevertheless, it is clear that there are some key characteristics of the contemporary international system which are powerfully conducive to terrorist violence. (Alona 1993).

Terrorist groups make no secret of their threats, they generally lose no opportunity of putting out their propaganda messages asserting the righteousness of their cause and the due consequences that face anyone who stands in their way. The problem of terrorism in the international system has serious implications at different levels. It is an intolerable attack on the individual human rights of the innocent. So far the United Nations General Assembly has been unable to agree on a standard definition of international terrorism. International terrorism can be distinguished from purely domestic terror violence by the presence of an international jurisdiction element. Most of the United Nations committees constituted have continually condemned acts of international terrorism.

According to Palmer (1970:126) the word terrorism was first popularized during the French Revolution in 1789 to establish order during the transient anarchical period of turmoil and upheaval that followed in the wake of many revolutions. It was an instrument of governance wielded by the established revolutionary state designed to consolidate the new government's power by intimidating counter revolutionaries, subversives and all other dissidents whom the new government regarded as enemies of the people.

By the 1930's the meaning of terrorism had changed again. It was now used less to refer to revolutionary movements and violence directed against governments and their leaders and more to describe the practices of mass repression employed by totalitarian states and their dictatorial leaders against their own citizens. Thus the term regained its former connotations of abuse of power by governments and was applied specifically to the authoritarian regimes that had come to power in fascist Italy, Nazi, Germany and Stalinist Russia. The accession to office by Hitler and Mussolini had depended in large measure on the street, the mobilization and deployment of gangs of brown-or black shirted thugs, to harass and intimidate political opponents. The most sinister dimension of this form of terror was that it became an intrinsic component of fascist and Nazi governance. A system of government sanctioned fear and coercion was thus created whereby political brawls, street fights and widespread persecution of Jews, communists and other

declared enemies of the state became the means through which complete and submissive compliance was ensured (Tucker 1990:271).

Conquest (1971:26) further noted that following the Second World War, terrorism regained the revolutionary connotations with which it is commonly associated today. At that time the term was used primarily in reference to the violent revolts then being prosecuted by the various indigenous nationalist/anti-colonialist groups that emerged in Asia, Africa and the Middle-East during the late 1940s and 1950s to oppose continued European rule. Countries as diverse as Israel, Kenya, Zimbabwe, Angola and Namibia for example, owe their independence at least in part to nationalist political movement that employed terrorism against colonial powers.

Many newly independent third world countries and communist bloc states in particular adopted this vernacular arguing that anyone or any movement that fought against colonial oppression and/or western domination should not be described as "terrorist" but were properly deemed to be "freedom fighters." This position was perhaps most famously explained by the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) Chairman, Yassir Arafat, when he addressed the United Nations General Assembly in November 1974. He was of the view that the difference between the revolutionary and the terrorist lies in the reason for which each fights for, whoever stands by a just cause and fights for the freedom and liberation of his land from the invaders, the settlers and the colonialists cannot possibly be called a terrorist (Arafat, 1976:51) In the same vein Sterling (1981:30) opined that during the late 1960s and 1970s, terrorism continued to be viewed within a revolutionary context. However, this usagenow expanded to include nationalist and ethnic separatists groups outside colonial or neo-colonial framework as well as radical ideologically motivated organizations.

Martin (1985:19) further noted that in the early 1980s, for example, terrorism came to be regarded as a calculated means to destabilize the West as part of a vast global conspiracy. By the middle of the decade, however a series of suicide bombings directed mostly against Americans diplomatic agents and United States military targets in the Middle East was focusing attention on the rising threat of state sponsored terrorism. According to MC Chung(1990), observed that various renegade foreign governments such as the regimes in Cuba, North Korea, Iran, Libya, Syria and Sudan became actively involved in sponsoring or commissioning terrorist acts. Terrorism thus became associated with a type of covert or surrogate warfare whereby weaker states could confront larger more powerful rivals without risk of retribution.

Similarly in the early 1990s the meaning and usage of the term "terrorism" were further blurred by the emergence of two new buzzwords, narco-terrorism and the so called gray area phenomenon. Narco-terrorism was defined as the use of drug

trafficking to advance the objectives of certain governments and terrorist organization identified as the Marxist-Leninist regimes of the former Soviet Union, namely Cuba, Bulgaria and Nicaragua. Criminal organizations were also sponsored by the communist bloc to undermine and forge strategic alliance with terrorist and guerilla organization. (Miller and Damask, 1996:114). In the 1990s terrorism began to be used to denote threats to the stability of nation states by non-state actors and non-governmental processes and organizations to describe violence affecting immense regions or urban areas where control had shifted from legitimate governments to political and criminal powers Corr (1993: XVIII).

Transnational terrorist attacks have captured the world's headlines in recent years bringing the horror of atrocity into millions of homes. Everyday, we read of desperate men and women bombing, assassinating, kidnapping, hijacking and blowing up installations all geared towards political motivation. Increasing global interdependence has led to terrorism becoming an international concern, involving nearly every nation state in the world, where as before, it had been confined to domestic disputes. The increasing incidence and impact of political terrorism over the last years have demonstrated that attempts by independent nations to deal with the problem are not adequate. The increasing nature of external support for terrorist operations, the possibility of terrorist escaping to safe haven across international boundaries and the switching of targets by terrorist to less well protected persons and property abroad as security at home improves are indicators of the transnational nature of much of political terrorism (Crenshaw 1989:5). Some rules of international law like those on territorial sovereignty and non-intervention have stood in the way of unilateral action by states to pursue and apprehend transnational terrorist. The attack on terrorism would be successful only if it were directed at the conditions which gave rise to terrorism.

Causes of Terrorism

Modern terrorism in the world today did not develop in a vacuum; it was a result of changes in political philosophy and governmental policies. More directly it reflected changes in the general attitude of the population, common people started to believe that governments should be controlled by citizens. Naturally some governments did not want to relinquish their control to the citizenry and scoffed at the idea of democracy (White 1998:151).

Terrorism has always been present in Western civilization in the sense that a government could be imposed through tactics of terror, but modern terrorist ideology was a product of the 1980s. It developed because several factors came into play to produce an environment allowing terrorism to grow. Some researchers believe that democracy was one of the most crucial factors in the development of Western terrorism (Stohl 1988). Without democracy, these analysts have argued that, revolutionary terrorism could not have survived.

Terrorist groups arise from a variety of conditions namely, deprivation, social injustice, nationalist or separatists tendencies, racial discrimination or religious differences, and these various discontented groups harbour long standing grievances against society (Palmer 1970).

According to Mac Wilson (1992:154). the basis of terrorism is political, economic or religious system of values, where the prevailing system and government in power is considered immoral or criminal. The revolutionary group believes itself to be superior both morally and in its analysis of society members. It believes that blackmailing the state is very important so that the state can grant economic, legal, political or religious advantages for that particular group. The primary aim is often intended to change the balance of power in the society.

Some analysts like Waldehum (1980:20) believe that social injustice and the denial of equal participation in a political system are the root cause of terrorism. They believe that if the causes were eliminated, terrorism would no longer have a motivation to develop. Terrorism could be eliminated by attacking poverty and injustice. Another theoretical contribution to the study is based on the assumption that terrorism like crime is spawned by social conditions. Terrorist like criminals are the product of their environment. They turn to violence because they have no other avenue to express their frustration. The ultimate treatment for the problem is to destroy the environment that produces violence. Several analysts support this premise. Rubenstein (1987:21) says that instead of attempting to profile the people involved in terrorist activities, we should ask why they engage in violence. He found his answer in the social conditions that bred violence. Rubenstein believes that improving those conditions would eliminate terrorism.

Mc Clung (1983:70) reflects this argument in a study in Ireland. He believes that the lack of opportunities for meaningful political expression and democratic change are the root cause of violence. Faced with government concessions, terrorist may increase their activities because they feel the government is weakening. Terrorism is also likely to arise when an alien hegemonic actor seeks to impose its political will on an antagonistic and large popular movement. Under these conditions foreign military intervention can succeed only if the popular movement can be intimidated or utterly destroyed.

Nationalistic Liberation Movements relying on force are aware of their inferiority in battlefield against national armies. These circumstances favour tactics based on surprise and dispersion that are regarded by the foreign adversary as provocative and improper, thereby inducing and justifying retaliatory attacks against the civilian movement of opposition. Terrorism thus becomes the only way viable, military strategy in these circumstances, which exist especially in the interaction between the west and the third world.

Another noteworthy work carried out by Lagueur (1987:6) maintains that social conditions have very little to do with terrorism. He returns to the repressionist argument to make this point. In the twentieth century Lagueur writes, evidence indicates that the more repressive a government becomes the less terrorism it suffers from. Social conditions are relatively immaterial. Lagueur points to Basque Nation and Liberty (ETA) terrorism as an example. Denying the repression caused by the Basque Nationalist and Liberty (ETA) revolt, he argues that Basque terrorism did not burst forth until the repressive hand of France was lifted.

Examination of the likely causes of terrorist activity suggests that terrorism is not perceived by all to be a disease. One man's terrorist is another man liberator. In fact, both governments and counter-government movement claim to seek liberty and both are labelled terrorists by those they oppose. The difference between freedom fighters and a protector of freedom often lies in the eye of the beholder, a problem that makes identity of a terrorist groups not altogether obvious. (Quinton, 1974:169).

Tactics of Terrorist

Transnational terrorist attacks have captured the world's headline in recent times bringing the horror of atrocity into millions of homes. It is also widely believed that terrorists are resorting to more spectacular incidents involving sophisticated technology and that terrorists aim at causing the greatest amount of death and destruction by their deeds. Whether the conclusion is correct can be evaluated by examining the tactics employed by terrorists that have inflicted serious damage to and casualties on the innocent population (Burton, 1971:11).

Different patterns of destructiveness and frequency emerge for each type of incident. Each type of incident requires different skills and access to equipment and logistic support planning, personnel intelligence and timing. Terrorism takes many forms, this ranges from threat to taking hostages, kidnapping, guerilla attacks, hijacking, indiscriminate shooting aerial hijacking and incendiary bombing (Jenkins, 1985:25).

(i) Barricade and Hostage Operation

Barricade and hostage taking constitute a common instrument. This is the illegal seizure of persons as objects for attaining their demands which often times are directed at governments or political organization. This was the case in the seizure of the representatives of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) and their staff in Vienna Austria in 1975. (Alexander 1989:117) Terrorist operations that have generated the greatest publicity, have had hostage seizure as their primary aim and have frequently resulted in casualties. Improvements in security measures at likely targets such as embassies and other

official installations have made this type of operation far more difficult to engage in, resulting in a noteworthy decline in 1980s.

(ii) Kidnapping

Kidnapping is another instrument of terrorism. Often times this is directed at high ranking officials in the government or political organization. It involves the abduction of the victim against his will. The hostage is usually viewed as a pawn to be used in obtaining concessions from the target of demands which might include the release of prisoners, payment of a monetary ransom and publication of political manifesto casualties are less frequent than popularly believed, with the hostage being released unharmed after the securing of concessions (Goldblatt-Burt, 1974:114).

(iii) Guerrilla Attacks

Guerrilla attacks have been used extensively by groups who cannot carry out conventional warfare because they cannot mobilize a military force the way the government does. This sudden attack method of hit and run has been used extensively in Latin America by the Tupamaros Revolutionary movement and the drug mafia terrorist groups in Uruguay, Peru and Columbia (Burton, 1971:48).

(iv) Hijacking

Hijacking has become the most common method of terrorism and often involves more victims than the other instruments. Often times, terrorists board aircraft as passengers with deadly weapons in their luggage or tucked in their dresses to avoid being noticed. After the journey has started these terrorists who pretended to be passengers draw up the pistols or automatic guns or hand grenade and direct the Captain to go where they want. Sometimes the hijackers are merely seeking a means of transportation to a nation giving them asylum. There are also situations in which the hijackers force the pilot to land the plane, release the passengers and crew and blow up the plane without making any ransom demands. This one has attracted perhaps the greatest attention by the press, (Rummel, 1966:65).

(v) Incendiary Bombing

Incendiary bombing is one of the easiest attacks to be mounted by terrorists due to its high frequency in comparison to other types of attacks. This is because of its ease of operation and low risk to the perpetrator. In the past years, incendiary attacks have risen in number while some difficult operations have grown more uncommon (Joll, 1964:74).

Terrorism is generally a group activity and group activities require some form of social organization. The purpose of a terrorist organization is to attack established political powers. To this end it must be organized well enough to launch a campaign, only relatively large groups have the ability to maintain a campaign of

terrorism. Therefore the goal of a terrorist group is first to appear large then to become larger.

In recent years terrorism has been primarily viewed as an international and foreign policy issue. Numerous acts of state-sponsored terrorists and foreign based groups, have given support to this notion. From another angle, terrorism may be seen as an instrument of foreign policy, a method directly pursued by states themselves to achieve their objectives abroad. The growth of international terrorism represents a trend in world politics that appears likely to continue because it offers an alternative mode of armed conflict to state and non-state actors alike. Given the cost and impracticality of conventional war, terrorism provides an available instrument of force that can be used (Crenshaw, 1989:58).

Terrorism like warfare has been condemned as a repugnant form of violence and defended as a necessary instrument of justice in the war against oppression and persecution. This argument has been used to justify terrorism (Gurt, 1988:30). Terrorists aim at eroding the support for the established leadership or undermine the authority of the state by destroying normality, creating uncertainty and polarising the country. Their action is a measure of deep frustration when there is no legitimate way to redress grievances. Frustrations escalate in its expression, developing from protest, violent demonstration, disruption and also sabotage. It also manifested in robbery activities, burning, bombing, casual killing to selective killing and kidnapping, when one level of the escalation fails, terrorists try the next level. Terrorists are always death seekers and generally take part in killings directed against anyone in authority. The greatest threat posed by terrorists now lies in the atmosphere of alarm they create, which corrodes democracy and breeds repression. If the government appears incompetent, public alarm will increase and so will the clamour for draconian measures (Jenkins, 1977:16).

It is manifest that states threatened by international terrorism cannot, in the present period give much credence to the idea of positive action by the international community. Threatened states and groups of states will have to rely on the inherent right of individual and collective self defence that is affirmed in Article 51 of the United Nations Charter. Some states have some instruments in their fight against terrorism directly at their disposal namely, more stringent customs procedures, stepped-up security of embassies and airports, development of screening profiles to identify terrorists, improved aircraft construction to partition passengers from pilots, bilateral and multilateral extradition agreements. Also coordinated intelligence and contingency planning, improved technology of electronic surveillance to detect metals and explosives, direct pressure on states which harbour terrorists are some of the instruments used in the fight against international terrorism. In addition to that, there has been the development of

clandestine counter terrorist organization to combat terrorists groups or to create incentives for other states to support actions against terrorism.

The Cost of International Terrorism

The most visible cost of terrorism is the tragic loss of life and injury caused by bombing, assassination, hijacking, kidnapping, sky hijacking and indiscriminate shooting on civilian targets. It is not possible to translate into economic terms the incalculable human suffering which result from terrorist attacks. International terrorism is not simply what terrorists do, but the effect, the publicity and the alarm they create by their actions. International terrorism appears to have increased markedly in the past few years; new incidents are reported almost weekly.

International terrorism represents a new kind of warfare. It is a warfare without territory, waged without armies as we know them. International terrorism has had a destabilizing effect on international order. Campaigns of terrorism or specific incidents of terrorism directed against targets in the foreign diplomatic or business community have embarrassed several governments, weakened some of them and no doubt contributed to the downfall of a few governments. International terrorism seems to be on the rise. It has increased fitfully during the last decade, and it is likely to persist into the next years to come.

Although it is legitimate to focus our attention on international terrorism because it poses specific problems for the world community, we should bear in mind that the term international terrorism is a somewhat artificial construct as it does not account for all the terrorist violence in the world. It excludes the considerable amount of violence carried out by terrorist operating within their own countries and against their own nationals and by many governments against their own citizens (Sick, 1990:99)

Terrorism has proved successful in several respects. It has been used as an effective means of propaganda. It has caused a great deal of disruption and substantial diversion of resources to security measures against terrorists.

The utility of an international approach in combating terrorism is a matter of some debate since it is by definition an international problem. Some believe the proper answer lies in formulating international Conventions skillfully framed so as to win widespread support and ratification. International Conventions and cooperation of the kind employed against pirates in the nineteenth century and against hijackers in the twentieth century is seen as the way to approach the problem. Some go further to argue for the creation of international bodies to assume the responsibility for responding to terrorist demands like international courts where captured terrorist may be tried and international prisons where

convicted terrorists may be incarcerated thereby protecting individual nations from being subjected to terrorist blackmail and retaliation (Mani, 1978:28)

Where terrorism has proved to be overwhelmingly effective is in the securing of publicity for groups actions and views. Dramatic actions are able to attract sensational seeking television and newspaper coverage, which tends to give an impression of strength that the group does not possess. They attempt to embarrass the government and corporations viewed as exploiters by releasing damaging information secured in interrogation of hostages or by theft of documents, as well as by clever maneuvering of hostage negotiating situations.

Conclusion

Terrorism is a special form of political violence which has been used by state and non-state actors for a variety of reasons terrorism is a direct threat to liberal democracy and to people's human rights it manifests itself through distinctive criminal acts calculated to harm human life, property and interest there are different types of terrorism. Terrorism has increased in the international system after issues such as injustice lack of democracy, violation of human rights, lack of problem accountability, religious intolerance poverty and lack of political will terrorism problem internally displaced person, refugees harmless. For today terrorism is a new face of underdevelopment in many third world countries

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